

Rev Fr General No Pomp and Show

VM Jose SJ

Papal Seminary, Pune

On 6th March 2019, the Superior General of the Society of Jesus visited Papal Seminary, Pune. On Ash Wednesday, he celebrated the Holy Eucharist in the Papal Seminary chapel for the whole campus and the JDV students.

I personally was eagerly waiting for his visit to Papal Seminary. I had only heard about him and his simplicity and casual way of dealing. When I met him, I realized that he is really a genuine, humble and ordinary person. Humility is the best way to keep oneself grounded and of this Earth. Humility is infectious. It has a magical quality to endear one to all. It starts with thoughts pure and serene. Humility is the essence of being human. Anyone can talk to him freely without considering his status. When he came to Pune, he was dressed in Pants and Kurta. He very easily adjusted himself to the place and situation. One of my desires was to have a photo with him. Of course, I did have several photos with him. It was like a dream come true in my life after I met him. I developed a deeper love for the Society of Jesus as I understood that the General is such a simple soul. I felt the desire to give back to the community a new sense of life, love, and spirit.

I must admit that it was a joyful experience meeting him and spending time with him. People like him can make a difference in the community and society. What is inspiring is that such great personalities can be such simple persons. No pomp and show were required to welcome him in our midst. The sharing that we had with him was also a learning experience. It was nice hearing from him news and information from Rome. Some people may think when great personalities come we wait for them to go back soon so that we have less tensions. However, according to me, I wished that he would stay longer with us.

While the experiences I have had during the visit have been spectacular, I have learned to truly value them and appreciate the Society. The Society of Jesus and persons like the General have enriched my life with his passion for learning and devotion to people.

A Prophet for Today

When I listened to Fr. General and interacted with him, I felt that he was truly a prophet. He was concerned of the poor and simple humans beings around us. He was truly rooted in prayer. He was deeply shaped by the traditions of the Society of Jesus.

He inspired us. Challenged us. And guided us. He reminded me of the Rev Fr Pedro Arrupe, whom I deeply admire. May Fr Arturo Sosa lead countless people to God through love and freedom!

Vincent Crasta SJ